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SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF DIACEREIN BY SOLID DISPERSION TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was solubility and dissolution rate enhancement of diacerein by using different solid dispersion techniques. Solid dispersion of diacerein was prepared by kneading and solvent evaporation method. Solid dispersions of diacerein with PEG-6000, guar gum and poloxamer-188 were prepared in different ratios as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3. FTIR, DSC and XRD were performed to study the interaction between drug and polymers. In solid dispersion formulations there was decrease in crystallinity of diacerein, which leads to increase in dissolution of diacerein from solid dispersions. All methods showed improvement in dissolution profile of diacerein as compare to pure drug. Kneading method shows faster drug release as compared to physical mixture and solvent evaporation method (diacerein and poloxamer -188) this might be due to kneading results in uniform distribution of drug in the polymer and forms the molecular and colloidal dispersion of drug in hydrophilic carrier and reduction of crystallinity of drug. As hydrophilic carrier dissolves, an insoluble drug is exposed to dissolution medium in the form of very fine particles, leading to rapid dissolution. Moreover other factors such as absence of aggregation and/or reagglomeration phenomenon during dissolution and particle size reduction could be attributed to a better dissolution profile.

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INTRODUCTION

The ultimate goal of drug product development is to design a system that maximizes therapeutic potential of the drug substance and facilitates its access to patients. Poorly water-soluble drug candidates often emerge from contemporary discovery programs and present formulation scientists with considerable technical challenges. With the advent of combinatorial chemistry and high throughput screening, the number of poorly water-soluble compounds has dramatically increased[1]. In pharmaceutical industry recently developed more than 40% new chemical entities are practically insoluble in water. These poorly water soluble drugs are allied with slow drug absorption leading to inadequate and variable bioavailability and gastrointestinal mucosal toxicity. There are different approaches used to enhance the aqueous solubility. The ability to increase aqueous solubility can thus be a valuable aid to increasing efficiency and/or reducing side effects for certain drugs. Various techniques are used to increase the solubility of poorly soluble drugs are chemical modifications, physical modifications techniques like media milling/ nanocrystal technology, cryogenic technology, supercritical fluid process, modification of the crystal habit, complexation, micellar technologies, other techniques like co-crystallization, co-solvency, hydrotrophy, solid dispersion [2].

Sekiguchi and Obi first introduced the concept of using solid dispersions to improve bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs in 1961[3]. Sekiguchi and Obi first time enhanced rate and extent of absorption of sulfathiazole using the solid dispersion technique[4]. It is defined as “dispersion of one or more active ingredients in an inert carrier or matrix at solid state prepared by fusion, solvent or melting solvent method”. Mayersohn and Gibaldi first used the solid dispersions may also be called solid-state dispersions[5].

Diacerein is 9, 10-dihydro-4, 5-dihydroxy-9, 10-dioxo-anthetharic acid diacetate, is NSAID used for the treatment of osteoarthritis[6-7]. It belongs to BCS class-II i.e. low solubility and high permeability. The solubility of diacerein, retards dissolution and results in poor bioavailability. So, enhancement of solubility useful to improve dissolution and ultimately bioavailability. The aim of the present study was to apply the principles of solid dispersions for solubility enhancement diacerein using different polymers as PEG-6000, guar gum, and poloxamer-188 by physical mixture, kneading method and solvent evaporation techniques.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

The following materials were used in this study. Diacerein (Elder Pharmaceuticals, Mumbai), PEG-6000, Poloxamer-188 (Shreya Laboratories, Aurangabad), Guar gum (Research lab fine chem. industries) All other chemicals used were analytical grade.

Methods:

Phase Solubility Study[8-9]:

Phase solubility of diacerein with PEG-6000, guar gum and poloxamer-188 was determined by the method reported by Huguchi and Connor, by dissolving excess amount of diacerein in 20 ml of distilled water containing increasing concentration of the PEG-6000/ Poloxamer-188 and Guar gum (i.e.1-5 % w/v) separately. Samples were shaken for 48 hrs at 37°C ± 0.5°C at constant speed and after 48 hrs samples were filtered. Absorbance of filtrate was measured spectrophotometrically at 257 nm. The phase solubility study was further carried out in 0.1N HCl (211 nm) and citrate buffer pH6 (340 nm).

Formulation of solid dispersion of Diacerein:

Solid dispersions of diacerein and PEG-6000, guar gum, poloxamer-188 were prepared by following methods:

Physical Mixture:

Physical mixtures were prepared by mixing weighed quantities of diacerein and polymer in various ratios (1:1, 1:2, 1:3) in a glass mortar for 15-20 min individually. These mixtures were then sifted through sieve no 80 for uniform size (table: 1).

Kneading Method:

Kneading mixtures of diacerein and polymer were prepared in different ratios (1:1,1:2,1:3) polymer was taken in mortar and wetted by adding small quantity of water till slurry like consistency is formed. Then drug was slowly incorporated into slurry and triturated for one hour. The paste was dried at 40°C in oven until dry, dried mass pulverized and sifted through sieve no 80 for uniform size (table: 1).

Solvent Evaporation:

Diacerein and polymers were accurately weighed in different ratios (1:1, 1:2, 1:3) separately. Diacerein was dissolved in methanol to get a clear drug solution and polymer was added to it with continuous stirring. Solvent was evaporated at room temperature for 24 hours. After drying product was crushed, pulverized and passed through sieve no.80 (table: 1).

Table 1. Formulations of solid dispersions of Diacerein + PEG - 6000, Diacerein + Guar gum, Diacerein + PXM-188 by different methods.

Method	Formulation			Drug Polymer Ratio
	Diacerein + PEG-6000	Diacerein + Guar gum	Diacerein + PXM-188	
Physical Mixture	F-1	F-10	F-19	1:1
	F-2	F-11	F-20	1:2
	F-3	F-12	F-21	1:3
Kneading Method	F-4	F-16	F-25	1:1
	F-5	F-17	F-26	1:2
	F-6	F-18	F-27	1:3
Solvent Evaporation	F-7	F-13	F-22	1:1
	F-8	F-14	F-23	1:2
	F-9	F-15	F-24	1:3

Evaluation of Solid Dispersion: Prepared solid dispersions were evaluated for:

Drug Content:

An accurately weighed quantity of solid dispersions equivalent to 50 mg of diacerein was taken into 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolved in 10 ml acetonitrile and diluted up to 100 ml using citrate buffer pH6, from this 5 ml solution taken and diluted to 50 ml with citrate buffer pH6 and then solution was filtered. Absorbance of filtrate was measured spectrophotometrically at 340 nm.

Drug excipient computability study:

FTIR analysis[10]:

Samples were prepared by grinding drug, excipient, physical mixture and solid dispersions with KBr (1:20) and then, pressing powder in the sample holder and placed in IR chamber and spectra of individual drug, excipients, their physical mixture and solid dispersions were obtained.

DSC Study[11]:

Thermogram of excipient, physical mixture and solid dispersions were obtained. Samples (3 mg) were sealed in flat bottomed aluminum pans and over a temperature range of 50-300°C at a rate of 10°C /min. in a nitrogen atmosphere using Shimadzu-60 DSC.

XRPD[12]:

Polymorphic nature of drug, physical mixture and solid dispersion was determined by X-ray powder diffraction technique. XRD patterns of were obtained by using Bruker D-8 X-Ray diffractometer at voltage of 40 kV and current of 40mA and scanning rate of 1° /min at diffraction angle of 2 theta degree using Cu (as anode) and radiation of wavelength 1.540600 Å.

In-vitro drug release study of solid dispersion formulations [6]:

An accurately weighed quantity of solid dispersions equivalent to 50 mg of diacerein was filled in hard gelatin capsule shell. The dissolution studies of capsule were conducted by using type I, IP (paddle method) dissolution test apparatus. The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml, citrate buffer pH6 as dissolution medium at temperature 37°C ± 0.5°C and paddle speed 75 rpm. Capsules were placed in sinker and when temperature of dissolution medium reached, put it in to dissolution medium. Aliquots of 5 ml was withdrawn at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45 min time intervals, filtered and samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium of same quantity to maintain volume of dissolution medium after each sampling and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 340 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Phase Solubility Study:

The solubility of diacerein was found to be 0.407 mcg/ml, 1.478 mcg/ml, 23.98 mcg/ml in distilled water, 0.1NHCl, citrate buffer pH6 respectively. Phase solubility was carried out using PEG-6000, guar gum and ploxamer-188 as carriers in different concentration range (1-5% w/v) in distilled water, 0.1N HCl and citrate buffer pH6. It was found that solubility of diacerein increases with increase in concentrations of polymers (table no 2, 3, 4).

The increase in solubility of diacerein was found due to effect of polymers in phases. The Gibb's free energy transfer (ΔG_{tr}) gives information about whether the treatment is favorable or unfavorable for drug solubilization. Negative Gibb's free energy values indicate improved dissolution. Gibb's free energy transfer (ΔG_{tr}) was calculated by using the following equation[13]:

$$\Delta G_{tr}^{\infty} = -20303 RT \log S_0/S_S \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where :

S_0/S_S = is the ratio of solubility of Diacerein in solution polymer to that of pure solution without polymer in same medium (gas constant)= 8.31 J.K⁻¹.mmol⁻¹, T = Temperature

Table (2,3,4) shows solubility and Gibb's free energy associated with the solubility of diacerein in poloxamer-188, guar gum and PEG-6000, in different media (distilled water, 0.1NHCl, citrate buffer pH6). It was found that solubility of diacerein increases with increase in polymer concentration due to formation of soluble complexes and/or cosolvent effect of carrier. The negative values of ΔG_{tr} was observed at all concentrations of polymers, indicated that the reaction becomes more favorable as the concentrations of polymers increased. Thus above polymers may be found to be promising tool to improve the solubility of diacerein.

Table 2 . Phase solubility (mcg/ml) and Gibb's free energy (kJ/mol at 37°C) of Diacerein in Poloxamer -188, Guar gum and PEG-6000 (Medium: Water).

Sr. No.	Concentration of Polymers (%w/v)	PXM-188		Guar gum		PEG-6000	
		Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	4.053	-707.12	2.175	-515.10	1.78	-352.13
3	2	5.34	-786.46	2.81	-594.45	2.375	-542.73
4	3	6.415	-848.10	4.455	-736.16	3.509	-662.82
5	4	8.791	-945.17	7.535	-897.70	5.345	-792.13
6	5	11.58	-1030.20	9.304	-962.18	6.915	-871.49

Table 3. Phase solubility (mcg/ml) and Gibb's free energy (kJ/mol at 37°C) of Diacerein in Poloxamer -188, Guar gum and PEG-6000 (Medium: 0.1 N HCl).

Sr. No.	Concentration of Polymers (%w/v)	PXM-188		Guar gum		PEG-6000	
		Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	6.51	-455.58	3.588	-272.85	2.775	-193.71
3	2	7.915	-516.30	4.744	-358.51	3.793	-289.78
4	3	11.51	-631.51	8.772	-547.69	4.679	-354.26
5	4	14.719	-707.18	10.75	-610.53	7.657	-505.88
6	5	20.595	-810.55	17.2976	-756.70	8.748	-546.52

Table 4. Phase solubility (mcg/ml) and Gibb's free energy of Diacerein(kJ/mol at 37°C) in Poloxamer -188, Guar gum and PEG-6000 (Medium: Citrate Buffer pH 6).

Sr. No.	Concentration of Polymers (%w/v)	PXM-188		Guar gum		PEG-6000	
		Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG	Solubility	ΔG
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	39.667	-154.45	31.559	-84.314	26.709	-33.159
3	2	52.488	-240.89	39.77	-155.16	32.028	-89.062
4	3	58.695	-275.33	40.258	-159.41	36.53	-129.66
5	4	61.546	-289.93	44.023	-186.34	36.664	-130.36
6	5	64.151	-302.54	46.691	-191.58	42.258	-174.29

Evaluation of Solid Dispersion:

Drug Content:

Drug content in solid dispersions of diacerein and polymers (PEG-6000, guar gum, and poloxamer-188) was found between 99.26 ± 0.850 to 100.50 ± 0.1 % w/w (Limit: 98-101% w/w).

FTIR analysis:

FTIR spectra of diacerein (Figure :1), showed characteristic peaks at 3070.88 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2985 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch, aliphatic symmetry), 3340 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch, aromatic), 1597 cm^{-1} (C=C stretch, aromatic), 1450 cm^{-1} (C-C, stretch, ester), 1103 cm^{-1} (ester shows characteristic -C-O-stretching bond), 1766 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch, ester), 1681 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch, COOH), 810 cm^{-1} (m-substituted benzene), 709 cm^{-1} (Benzene). FTIR spectra of diacerein and PEG-6000, physical mixture formulation F-3 (Figure:1) shows slight shifting of characteristic peaks of diacerein from 3070.88 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch, aromatic), 2985 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch, aliphatic symmetry), 3340 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch, aromatic), 1450 cm^{-1} (C-C, stretch, ester) to 3070.78 cm^{-1} , 2885.60 cm^{-1} , 3325.99 cm^{-1} , 1465.95 cm^{-1} respectively which might be due to dilution effects of excipient. There were no new band are observe in above spectra indicating absence of chemical bond formation/interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and PEG-6000, kneading method formulation F-6 (Figure:1) shows shifting of peaks slightly to higher frequency, from 1450.52 cm^{-1} , 1681.98 cm^{-1} to 1465.95 cm^{-1} , 1697.41 cm^{-1} and shifting of some peaks to lower frequency from 2885.91 cm^{-1} , 3340.52 cm^{-1} to 3325 cm^{-1} indicating physical interaction between diacerein and PEG-6000 due to kneading and solvent indicates formation of solid dispersion. Also there is no formation of any new peaks indicating absence of chemical bond formation and chemical interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and PEG-6000, solvent evaporation formulation F-9 (Figure :1) shows shifting of peaks from 709.83 cm^{-1} , 1450.52 cm^{-1} , 2858.91 cm^{-1} , 3340.82 cm^{-1} , 1026.16 cm^{-1} to 702.11 cm^{-1} , 1465.95 cm^{-1} , 2885.60 cm^{-1} , 3325 cm^{-1} , 1057.03 cm^{-1} indicating strong physical interaction between drug and polymer in presence of methanol. Also there is no formation of any new peaks indicating absence of chemical bond formation and chemical interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and guar gum, physical mixture (Figure: 1) shows at 1597.11 cm^{-1} (C=C stretch, aromatic), 1450.52 cm^{-1} (C-C, stretch, ester), 1766.85 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch, ester) 1681.98 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch, COOH), 810.13 cm^{-1} (m-substituted benzene), 702.11 cm^{-1} (Benzene), 3070 cm^{-1} (C-H, aromatic ring) shows slight shifting of some characteristic peaks of diacerein which might be due to higher concentration of polymer and dilution effect of polymer. There were no new band are observe in above spectra indicating absence of chemical bond formation/interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and guar gum by kneading method formulation F-18 (Figure:1) shows 3070.78 cm^{-1} and 4019.79 cm^{-1} (-O-H group ,but it is increases due to free hydrogen bonding with water), 1211 cm^{-1} and 1288 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching, it is nearer to -OH group), 1435 cm^{-1} and 1597 cm^{-1} (cyclic member ring with polysubstituent). The changes in frequencies are observed due to addition of water during kneading and hydrogen bonding with oxygen in drug. There is no new peaks observed, indicating absence of chemical bond formation in the binary system.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and guar gum, by solvent evaporation method formulation F-15 (Figure:1), shows peaks at 810.13 cm^{-1} and 902.72 cm^{-1} (-C-H group), 1026.16 cm^{-1} , 1211.34 cm^{-1} and 1288.49 cm^{-1} (-C-O, ether), 1597.11 cm^{-1} and 1766.85 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch, ester), 2360.95 cm^{-1} and 4027.5 cm^{-1} (-O-H group) ,the changes in frequencies are observed due to hydrogen bonding with oxygen in drug. Also there is no formation of any new peaks indicating absence of chemical bond formation and chemical interaction between drug and polymer.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and poloxamer-188 physical mixture (Figure:1) shows 702.11 cm^{-1} (Benzene), 1026.16 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch ester) 1465.95 cm^{-1} (C-O, Stretch, COOH), 1681.98 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch aromatic), 1766.85 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch, ester), 2885.6 cm^{-1} (carboxylic acid), 3340.82 cm^{-1} (O-H stretch, broad, COOH). Shifting of peaks observed due to dilution effect of excipient. There is no new peak appear in spectra of physical mixture indicates absence of chemical interaction between diacerein and poloxamer-188.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and poloxamer-188 by kneading method (Figure :1) shows peaks at 702.11 cm^{-1} (Benzene), 1026.16 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch ester), 1465.95 cm^{-1} (C-O, Stretch, COOH), 1597.11 cm^{-1} (C=C stretch ,aromatic), 1681.98 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch aromatic), 1766.85 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch, ester), 2885.6 cm^{-1} (carboxylic acid). The changes in frequencies are observed due to addition of water during kneading and hydrogen bonding with oxygen in drug. There is no new peaks observed, indicating absence of chemical bond formation in the binary system.

FTIR spectra of diacerein and poloxamer-188 by solvent evaporation method formulation, F-24 (Figure:1) shows peaks at 702.11 cm^{-1} (Benzene), 1026.16 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch ester), 1465.95 cm^{-1} (C-O, Stretch, COOH), 1597.11 cm^{-1} (C=C stretch ,aromatic), 1681.98 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch aromatic), 1766.85 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretch, ester), 2885.6 cm^{-1} (carboxylic acid). The changes in frequencies are observed due to solvent effect i.e. methanol and hydrogen bonding with oxygen in drug. There is no new peaks observed, indicating absence of chemical bond formation in the binary system.

All solid dispersion systems shows shifting of characteristic peaks intensity and disappearance of characteristics IR band of either by drug or polymers indicating alteration in drug or polymer environment or may be due to surface absorption of polymer.

Figure 1. Fourier transform infrared images of Diacerein and its solid dispersion formulations.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry:

DSC thermogram of diacerein (Figure: 2) showed a sharp endothermic peak at 261°C ascribed to melting of crystalline diacerein, with enthalpy of -304.57 mJ , peak height -19.28m/W, onset temperature at 259°C and end set temperature at 252.94°C. In DSC thermogram of physical mixture sharp endothermic peak of diacerein appears with decrease in peak height due to dilution effect of excipient (Higher concentration of polymers). Solvent evaporation and kneading method shows changes in peak characteristics due to formation of solid dispersion. The changes in crystallinity and surface morphology were studied by using XRD technique. It was found that formed solid dispersions were amorphous in nature.

Figure 2. Differential scanning calorimetry thermograms of Diacerein and its solid dispersion formulations.

Powder X-ray Diffraction Analysis (XRD):

Crystallinity of diacerein was determined by XRD. In XRD degree of crystallinity of any material can be determined from peak intensity in spectra, more the peak intensity more the crystallinity. Figure: 3 shows XRD spectra of diacerein and its solid dispersion formulations, pure diacerein having major characteristic high intensity peaks at diffraction angle of 2θ at 5.1989°, 17.3307°, 27.772°, 24.9876° with peak intensity 24599,48897,41543,18579 respectively indicating crystalline nature of diacerein. Crystallinity was determined by comparing some representative peak heights in the diffraction patterns of the binary system with those of reference. The relationship used for calculation of crystallinity is relative degree of crystallinity (RDC) was calculated from the ratio of highest peak intensity of formulation to highest peak intensity of drug. All formulations shows decrease in relative degree of crystallinity indicates decrease in crystalline nature of drug.

Figure 3. Powder X-ray diffraction spectra of Diacerein and its solid dispersion formulations.

In-vitro drug release study of solid dispersion formulations:

Dissolution profile of diacerein is shown in table : 5 and figure:4. Dissolution rate of diacerein at 5, 15, 30 and 45 minutes were 4.616, 6.742, 9.588, 11.834 % respectively. The slowest dissolution rate of diacerein was due to its hydrophobicity that leads to floating of powder on the surface of dissolution medium and prevents its surface contacting the medium. It clears that drug having poor dissolution and needs to further dissolution enhancement.

Table 5. In-vitro drug release of Diacerein API, Diacerein + PEG - 6000 solid dispersion formulations (Physical Mixture: F-1,F-2,F-3), (Kneading Method: F-4,F-5,F-6),(Solvent Evaporation:F-7,F-8,F-9).

Time (Min.)	Drug Release (%)									
	Diacerein	F-1 (1:1)	F-2 (1:2)	F3 (1:3)	F-4 (1:1)	F-5 (1:2)	F-6 (1:3)	F-7 (1:1)	F-8 (1:2)	F-9 (1:3)
5	4.616 ± 0.545	2.203 ±1.56	3.686 ±0.383	5.656 ±0.452	4.944 ± 0.171	5.885 ±0.19	7.57 ±0.409	5.643 ±0.455	6.659 ±0.249	8.74 ±0.101
10	5.984 ± 0.496	5.461 ±0.858	10.962 ±4.62	9.862 ±1.062	7.999 ± 1.44	11.840 ±0.252	15.727 ±0.266	11.175 ±0.551	13.893 ±0.510	14.047 ±3.17
15	6.742 ± 0.883	14.470 ±3.96	24.204 ±3.39	16.709 ±2.803	16.052 ± 0.577	36.641 ±0.579	38.927 ±0.542	34.685 ±0.517	36.261 ±0.637	39.207 ±0.665
20	7.286 ± 0.924	22.782 ±3.38	37.554 ±3.130	35.649 ±4.53	31.582 ±2.195	50.536 ±0.695	59.772 ±0.925	45.458 ±1.534	52.862 ±0.658	57.837 ±0.960
25	8.35 ±0.850	26.071 ±4.100	47.076 ±3.22	52.690 ±2.358	41.470 ±0.888	59.872 ±0.641	67.951 ±1.551	51.157 ±0.879	62.912 ±1.054	68.117 ±1.559
30	9.588 ± 0.860	38.391 ±3.030	53.855 ±3.077	61.539 ±3.30	52.069 ±1.104	66.908 ±0.501	71.781 ±1.284	63.800 ±0.754	68.205 ±0.558	71.530 ±0.745
35	10.888 ± 0.714	46.531 ±1.082	59.625 ±2.014	69.471 ±1.102	68.805 ±0.654	71.085 ±0.758	77.179 ±0.297	69.044 ±0.523	72.607 ±0.948	77.091 ±0.971
40	11.21 ± 0.800	56.967 ±1.38	66.088 ±0.914	72.816 ±1.41	71.329 ±1.142	75.069 ±0.647	80.195 ±0.327	71.528 ±0.307	75.725 ±0.546	78.379 ±0.360
45	11.83 ±0.647	63.150 ±0.362	70.704 ±0.982	76.377 ±0.696	75.145 ±0.178	80.61 ±0.432	85.097 ±0.150	72.375 ±0.637	77.713 ±0.672	80.536 ±0.532

Figure 4. In-vitro drug release of Diacerein API, Diacerein + PEG-6000 solid dispersion formulations(Physical Mixture: F-1,F-2,F-3), (Kneading Method: F-4,F-5,F-6),(Solvent Evaporation:F-7,F-8,F-9).

Physical mixture of diacerein and PEG-6000 (table: 5 and figure: 4) shows increase in drug release as compared to pure diacerein. Physical mixture of diacerein and PEG-6000 in different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 63.150, 70.704 and 76.377% respectively at 45 minutes, where as pure drug shows only 11.834% at 45 minutes. As the concentration of polymer in physical mixture increases it leads to increase in dissolution rate of drug and could be attributed due to the improved wettability of diacerein particles or the formation of soluble complex with PEG-6000, a hydrophilic polymer, that leads to decrease in interfacial tension between hydrophobic drug and dissolution medium and leads to increase in wetting and surface available for dissolution. Also it was found that pure drug float on the surface dissolution medium whereas drug carrier mixtures sink immediately in dissolution medium.

Solid dispersion of diacerein and PEG-6000 prepared by solvent evaporation method in different ratio 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 72.375, 77.713, and 80.536 % at 45 minutes (table : 5 and figure : 4). It shows better release as compared to physical mixture due to the formation of molecular dispersions with high surface free energy resulting in the pull of insoluble but discrete drug molecules into bulk of solvent as dissolved entity and additionally due to absence of aggregation and/or reagglomeration phenomenon during dissolution.

Solid dispersion of diacerein and PGE-6000 prepared by kneading method shows faster dissolution as compared to physical mixture and solvent evaporation. Physical mixture of diacerein and PEG-6000 in different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 63.150, 70.704 and 76.377% respectively at 45 minutes and solid dispersion of solvent evaporation 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 72.375, 77.713, 80.536 % at 45 minutes where as kneading method solid dispersion of different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows 75.145, 80.61, 85.097 % respectively at 45 minutes (table: 5 and figure: 4), this might be due to kneading results in uniform distribution of drug in the polymer and forms the molecular and colloidal dispersion of drug in hydrophilic a carrier. When such dispersion comes in contact with dissolution medium leads to dissolution of hydrophilic carrier and cause precipitation of drug into fine particles, leads to increase in surface available for dissolution. Other factors such as absence of aggregation and/or reagglomeration phenomenon during dissolution and particle size reduction could be attributed to better dissolution.

Physical mixture and solid dispersions of diacerein with PEG-6000 shows improvement in dissolution profile of drug as compared to pure drug. A PEG-6000 lead to improvement is dissolution of diacerein. PEG-6000 able to dissolve more of the drug leading to a greater percentage drug in the molecularly dispersed form and that the higher viscosity of the PEG -6000 hindered precipitation of the drug following dissolution of carrier. Also in this molecular weight (6000) the water solubility of PEG-6000 is still very high but hygroscopy is not problem and melting point is 50 °C. If low molecular weight PEG used leads to formation of sticky product.

Physical mixture of diacerein and guar gum (table :6 and figure: 5) shows increase in drug release as compared to pure diacerein. Physical mixture of diacerein and guar gum in different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 61.414, 65.519 and 71.439 % respectively at 45 minutes, where as pure drug shows only 11.834% at 45 minutes. It might be due to hydrophilic nature of polymer which helps to increase in wettability of drug and hence drug release.

Solid dispersion of diacerein and guar gum prepared by solvent evaporation method in different ratio 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 73.128, 76.046, and 80.571 % at 45 minutes (table:6 and figure: 5). It shows better release as compared to physical mixture due to the hydrophilic nature of the carrier, hydrodynamic microenvironment was changes and drug get dispersed in to polymer which prevents aggregation and/or reagglomeration phenomenon during dissolution.

Table 6. *In-vitro* drug release of Diacerein API, Diacerein + Guar gum solid dispersion formulations (Physical Mixture: F-10, F-11,F-12), (Solvent Evaporation:F-13,F-14,F-15), (Kneading Method: F-16,F-17,F-18).

Time (Min.)	Drug Release (%)									
	Diacerein	F-10 (1:1)	F-11 (1:2)	F-12 (1:3)	F-13 (1:1)	F-14 (1:2)	F-15 (1:3)	F-16 (1:1)	F-17 (1:2)	F-18 (1:3)
5	4.616 ± 0.545	3.986 ±0.474	5.581 ±0.528	8.154 ±0.581	4.788 ±0.300	6.815 ±0.069	7.761 ±0.233	5.591 ±0.767	6.665 ±0.421	9.233 ±0.517
10	5.984 ± 0.496	5.114 ±0.906	7.336 ±1.059	11.462 ±0.111	10.119 ±0.710	11.524 ±0.273	30.175 ±0.722	8.080 ±0.704	15.366 ±0.750	30.255 ±2.070
15	6.742 ± 0.883	10.915 ±0.213	12.820 ±1.152	20.734 ±0.350	15.078 ±1.274	16.091 ±0.093	41.543 ±0.448	16.050 ±0.518	21.593 ±0.670	31.717 ±1.26
20	7.286 ± 0.924	24.395 ±0.181	27.736 ±0.536	29.941 ±0.314	39.014 ±0.723	40.280 ±0.153	52.025 ±0.540	24.245 ±0.560	35.300 ±0.513	45.406 ±0.969
25	8.35 ± 0.850	29.671 ±0.158	31.199 ±0.611	39.770 ±0.100	45.909 ±0.437	47.674 ±0.175	58.545 ±0.377	35.244 ±0.509	51.672 ±1.69	58.300 ±0.352
30	9.588 ± 0.860	41.564 ±0.535	48.610 ±0.494	50.012 ±0.165	58.467 ±0.309	61.751 ±0.053	60.524 ±0.574	48.743 ±0.903	65.557 ±3.01	63.457 ±1.280
35	10.888 ± 0.714	46.928 ±0.705	55.049 ±0.646	58.125 ±1.029	64.386 ±0.740	70.434 ±0.330	72.354 ±0.705	60.659 ±0.471	74.960 ±1.409	74.624 ±1.02
40	11.21 ± 0.800	54.568 ±0.528	62.671 ±1.150	66.381 ±0.053	67.454 ±0.396	71.911 ±0.789	75.447 ±0.755	60.051 ±1.28	75.073 ±3.025	78.684 ±0.470
45	11.834 ± 0.647	61.414 ±0.470	65.519 ±0.190	71.439 ±0.563	73.128 ±0.245	76.046 ±0.062	80.571 ±0.504	77.129 ±0.622	80.35 ±0.518	84.55 ±0.555

Figure 5 *In-vitro* drug release of formulation of Diacerein API, Diacerein + Guar gum solid dispersion formulations (Physical Mixture: F-10,F-11,F-12), (Solvent Evaporation:F-13,F-14,F-15), (Kneading Method: F-16,F-17,F-18).

Solid dispersion of diacerein and guar gum prepared by kneading method (table :6 and figure: 5) shows faster dissolution as compared to physical mixture and solvent evaporation. Guar gum in different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 77.129, 80.350, and 84.550 % respectively at 45 minutes, this might be due to kneading results in uniform distribution of drug in the polymer and forms the molecular and colloidal dispersion of drug in hydrophilic a carrier.

Guar gum is used in solid dosage form as binder and disintegrant. However due to swelling ability of the carrier profound influence on the improvement in dissolution of poorly water soluble drugs. Due to the hydrophilic nature of the carrier hydrodynamic microenvironment around the particles was changed. At time of dissolution, drug and carrier from mixtures comes in contact with dissolution fluid, passing of dissolution medium into drug carrier particles takes place, which initiates the formation of stagnant gel layer of carrier around the particles. During dissolution process the drug particles that are not agglomerated but disperse rapidly throughout dissolution medium and expose a greater surface area, resulting in rapid drug release.

Physical mixture of diacerein and poloxamer-188 (table: 7 and figure :6) shows increase in drug release as compared to pure diacerein. Physical mixture of diacerein and poloxamer-188 in different ratio as 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 shows drug release of 71.250, 75.980 and 78.080% respectively at 45 minutes, where as pure drug shows only 11.834% at 45 minutes. Improvement in drug dissolution in physical mixture might be due to surfactant effect of poloxamer which creates a polymeric micellar microenvironment around drug particle and leads to increase in wettability of drug particles and increased in rate of mass transfer from the surface of drug particles.

Table 7. *In-vitro* drug release of Diacerein API, Diacerein + Ploxamer-188 solid dispersion formulations (Physical Mixture: F-19,F-20,F-21), (Solvent Evaporation:F-22,F-23,F-24), (Kneading Method: F-25,F-26,F-27).

Time (Min.)	Drug Release (%)									
	Diacerein	F-19 (1:1)	F-20 (1:2)	F-21 (1:3)	F-22 (1:1)	F-23 (1:2)	F-24 (1:3)	F-25 (1:1)	F-26 (1:2)	F-27 (1:3)
5	4.616 ± 0.545	4.30 ±1.16	6.950 ±0.148	7.366 ±0.476	7.832 ±0.382	8.864 ±0.254	9.781 ±0.216	11.554 ±0.483	14.052 ±0.69	15.070 ±0.107
10	5.984 ± 0.496	11.260 ±1.378	10.135 ±0.377	15.52 ±0.922	28.698 ±1.009	34.083 ±0.833	37.362 ±1.179	33.195 ±0.974	36.200 ±0.489	40.120 ±0.511
15	6.742 ± 0.883	21.593 ±0.128	16.804 ±0.286	22.723 ±0.334	39.410 ±0.721	49.982 ±0.757	56.078 ±0.943	60.662 ±0.472	69.326 ±0.166	75.556 ±0.227
20	7.286 ± 0.924	29.678 ±0.560	38.483 ±0.601	40.785 ±0.490	57.038 ±0.415	58.007 ±0.551	65.738 ±0.583	74.667 ±0.185	78.643 ±0.148	80.475 ±0.288
25	8.35 ± 0.850	39.166 ±0.657	47.820 ±0.512	57.938 ±0.158	60.994 ±0.709	63.196 ±0.670	77.228 ±0.660	77.387 ±0.566	80.515 ±0.518	82.540 ±0.380
30	9.588 ± 0.860	48.332 ±0.398	55.007 ±0.166	66.909 ±0.193	70.290 ±0.664	73.068 ±1.471	78.953 ±0.206	79.721 ±0.159	82.532 ±0.466	87.530 ±1.425
35	10.888 ± 0.714	57.176 ±0.534	60.499 ±0.634	71.157 ±0.562	75.973 ±0.132	80.999 ±0.135	80.362 ±0.295	85.242 ±0.215	88.802 ±0.114	89.455 ±0.428
40	11.21 ± 0.800	64.913 ±0.532	73.005 ±1.028	75.502 ±0.593	78.830 ±0.189	84.784 ±0.760	86.461 ±0.633	88.669 ±0.486	90.720 ±0.197	91.710 ±0.239
45	11.834 ± 0.647	71.250 ±0.232	75.980 ±0.188	78.080 ±1.005	80.330 ±0.805	85.161 ±0.075	88.580 ±0.820	90.260 ±0.143	92.256 ±0.227	94.626 ±0.257

Figure 6. *In-vitro* drug release of Diacerein API, Diacerein + Ploxamer-188 solid dispersion formulations (Physical Mixture: F-19, F-20, F-21), (Solvent Evaporation: F-22, F-23, F-24), (Kneading Method: F-25, F-26, F-27).

Drug release of diacerein and poloxamer-188 solid dispersion by solvent evaporation shown in table: 7 and figure: 6. Solvent evaporation showed faster drug release i.e. 88.580% (1:3 ratio) as compared to physical mixture i.e. 78.080 % (1:3 ratio) and pure drug 11.834% (1:3 ratio) at 45 minutes. The increase in drug release can be attributed to the formation of molecular dispersions with higher surface free energy resulting in pull of insoluble but discrete drug molecules into the bulk of solvent as dissolved entity. Additionally solubilization effect of poloxamer-188 micelles prevents reaggregation of drug molecules. Presence of amorphous drug in crystalline carrier. This can be correlated to results of XRD which shows decrease in crystallinity of drug in solid dispersion. Poloxamer-188 shows better drug release as compare to other polymers i.e. PEG-6000 and guar gum. It exists in solution as unimers but self assemble into micelles. At concentration above CMC, a hydrophilic propylene oxide core can incorporate water insoluble molecules resulting in increased solubility of the drug molecules. In addition, greater hydrophilicities and surfactant properties of poloxamer result in reduction interfacial tension between drug and dissolution medium leading to increased wettability of drug, dispersibility and reduced particle size of the drug might contribute to dissolution diacerein.

Kneading method showed faster drug release (table: 5,6,7 and figure: 4,5, 6) as compared to physical mixture and solvent evaporation method formulations of diacerein and poloxamer-188, this might be due to kneading results in uniform distribution of drug in the polymer and forms the molecular and colloidal dispersion of drug in hydrophilic a carrier and reduction of crystallinity of drug. As hydrophobic carrier dissolves, an insoluble drug is exposed to dissolution medium in the form of very fine particles, leading to rapid dissolution. Moreover other factors such as absence of aggregation and/or reagglomeration phenomenon during dissolution & particle size reduction could be attributed to a better dissolution profile.

CONCLUSION:

From the study it was found that kneading and solvent evaporation methods for preparation of solid dispersion lead to improvement in dissolution profile of diacerein. Kneading method shows faster drug release as compared to physical mixture and solvent evaporation method this might be due to kneading results in uniform distribution of drug in the polymer and forms the molecular and colloidal dispersion of drug in hydrophilic a carrier and reduction of crystallinity of drug. Poloxamer-188 shows better drug release as compare to other polymers i.e. PEG-6000 and guar gum. From the above study it can be concluded that solid dispersion technique (kneading, solvent evaporation) is useful for the solubility enhancement of poorly water soluble drugs.

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ABBREVIATIONS:

PEG-6000	: Polyethylene glycol 6000
FTIR	: Fourier Transform Infrared
DSC	: Differential Scanning Calorimetry
XRD	: X-ray powder diffraction
NSAID	: Non steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
BCS	: Biopharmaceutical Classification System
Hrs	:hours
PXM-188	: Poloxamer-188
Rpm	: Revolutions per minute
RDC	: relative degree of crystallinity
CMC	: Critical micelle concentration

Conflict of interest:

The authors do not report any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Shah NH, Phuapradit W, Zhang YE, Sandhu H, Zhang L, Malick W. Approaches for improving bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs. In Aussburger LL, Stephen Hoag WS, editors. *Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms: Tablets.3 ed.* Vol. 02. New York, London: Informa healthcare; 2008. pp.51.
2. Chaudhary A, Nagaich U, Gulati N, Sharma VK, Khosa RL. Enhancement of solubilization and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs by physical and chemical modifications: A recent review. *J Adv Pharm Edu Res* .2012; 2 (1) :32-67.
3. Debjit B, Harish G, Duraivel S, Kumar BP, Raghuvanshi V, Kumar KPS. Solid Dispersion: A Approach To Enhance The Dissolution Rate of Poorly Water Soluble Drugs. *The Pharm Innov J*. 2013; 1(12): 25-38.
4. Thakur K, Nagpal M, Aggarwal G, Kaur R, Singh S, Behl *et al.* Jain A review on solid dispersion *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2014;9(3):173-187.
5. Chiou WL, Riegelman S. Pharmaceutical application of solid dispersion. *J Pharm Sci*. 1971; 60(9):1281-1302.
6. Indian Pharmacopoeia, Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ghaziabad. Govt. of India Ministry of Health and family welfare, New Delhi, 2014, Vol II, 1543-1545, 1718.
7. <http://www.drugs.com/international/diacerein.html>.
8. Higuchi T, Connors A. Phase Solubility techniques. In: *Advances in analytical chemistry instrumentation*. New York, NY: Wiley Interscices; 1965. pp.117-211.
9. Patel SG, Rajput SJ. Enhancement of oral bioavailability of Cilostazaol by forming its inclusion complexes. *AAPS Pharm Sci Tech*. 2009; 10(2): 660-669.
10. Karthikeyan S. UV-Visible and infrared analysis of commercial drug and its mixtures. *Arch Phy Res*. 2011; 2 (4):72-79.
11. Van Dooren AV, Duphar BV, Weesp. Design for drug excipient interaction study. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm*. 1983; 9(1-2):43-55.
12. Wanare RS. Studies on enhancement of dissolution of poorly water soluble drug by solid dispersion technique. *Int J Comp Pharm*. 2013; 03 (05):1-5.
13. Zaki RM, Ali] AA, Menshawi SFE, Bary AA. Effect of binary and ternary solid dispersions prepared by fusion method on the dissolution of poorly water soluble diacerein. *Int J Drug Del*. 2013; 5:99-109.

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